

TRADE RECEIVABLES AND / OR PAYABLES? EVIDENCE OF THEIR IMPACT ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

Purpose – The main objective of the research was to identify the impact of trade receivables and payables on financial performance for a sample of car parts companies.

Methodology/approach – Since most of the companies in the sample are medium-sized (unlisted) companies, we used accounting measures. The dependent variable was return on assets and return on equity; the independent variable was trade receivables, trade payables and net trade credit, firm size and growth rate. Eviews 9 software was used to formulate econometric models.

Findings – The results of this study are in line with previous research results and confirm that trade receivables and payables have a negative impact on financial performance.

Research limitations/implications – Empirical research was conducted on a sample of companies selected based on several criteria. The extension of the sample and the grouping of companies (according to the size criterion) can increase the degree of representativeness of the research results.

Practical implications – The research is useful because it provides empirical evidence; managers can capitalize on research results for a proper substantiation of funding and performance strategies.

Originality/value – Research results are valuable contributions towards the improvement of Romanian companies' performance.

Key words: performance, trade receivables, trade payables.

Introduction

Integrated in the field of performance management, measuring financial performance is one of the longest-lived preoccupation for academia and business. In this study we will consider financial performance as an artefact based on which the success of an organization is appreciated, in the context of a globalized market. Maintaining or increasing a company's performance requires careful management of trade receivables and payables to identify the extent to which they balance. Research conducted in the US and Europe has shown that trade receivables granted by companies accounted for 9% of total sales revenue, and 94% of these receivables were financed from trade payables (Afrifa and Gyapong, 2017).

The research on this field has expanded in recent decades. However, things are not completely clear. The diversity of data and indicators analysed, the diversity of samples but also of the methodologies used made the research results mixed, and difficult to generalize. For these reasons, but also to ensure the representativeness of the results, the main objective of the research is to identify the impact of trade receivables and payables on financial performance for a sample of companies producing car exchange parts for vehicles, for a period of 10 years. To achieve this objective, we structured the work as follows. The first section presents a review of the literature on performance and trade receivables and payables; the second section details the research methodology; the next section presents the research results; the last section summarizes discussion and conclusions.

Review of the literature on financial performance, trade receivables and payables

Financial performance appraisal systems have been developed in several stages (Rajnoha, Lesníková and Korauš, 2016). In the first stage (until 1980), the financial indicators underlying the evaluations were profit and profitability (assets, capital, investments). Over the next ten years, performance management systems focused on creating value for stakeholders, and the indicators used were economic added value (for the company and stakeholders). In this context, financial performance has been defined as the ability of a company to create economic value (Orozco Vargas and Galindo-Dorado, 2018), to maximize the wealth of its shareholders or founders (Baker, Veit and Powell, 2001), to attract and generate profits for investors (Suhadak et al., 2019; Al-Sa'eed, 2018). Then, as an effect of the intensification of globalization, the evaluation of financial performance was performed in an integrated framework, along with other facets of performance, based on methods such as business excellence, balance score card, service profit chain, integrated performance measurement. Against the background of divergences on the indicators used to measure performance, new methods have been proposed, called multi-criteria methods that operate either with a single synthesis indicator or with a multiple combination of partial indicators (Peleckis, Krutinis and Slavinskaitė, 2013).

Recently, new performance measurement systems have been developed: dynamic multi-dimensional performance framework; integrated performance measurement framework; holistic performance management framework. Some authors (Batrancea et al, 2018) showed that the studies regarding performance link five major categories of causality: growth and performance; working capital and performance; capital market and profitability; cash flow and earnings; capital structure and profitability. In this study we focus on the link between working capital and performance. As a consequence of sales-purchase relationships, companies simultaneously generate trade receivables and payables. The issue of trade receivables and payables is integrated into research regarding the impact of short-term financing on financial performance.

Debt-based financing theory admits that a company that holds receivables from its customer relationships can improve profitability but also overall performance by virtue of favourable customer relationships, which can guarantee future sales. As the period of receivables increases, the supplier has more control over customers and can cause them to buy more than necessary (Afrifa and Padachi, 2016), especially when there are a small number of suppliers on the market (Garcia-Teruel and Martinez-Solano, 2010). On the other hand, trade receivables restrict the possibilities of financing the current activity, which is why some researchers have opined that their volume must be minimal or even zero (Afrifa and Gyapong, 2017). The arguments invoked were: companies with higher liquidity may be more profitable (Goddard, Tavakoli and Wilson, 2005); the volume of trade receivables must be assessed according to the size of the company (Petersen and Rajan, 1997) and to the possibilities of access to the capital market (Hill, Kelly and Highfield, 2010; Banos-Caballero et al., 2010).

Liquidity theory explains why companies use supplier credit as a source of financing. Treated as a substitute for institutional financing (from banks), the credit provider can improve the financial performance of the beneficiary companies provided with the condition that to be a cheaper source of financing. Research has shown that companies with financing difficulties register an increase in trade payables (Atanasova, 2007; Molina and Preve, 2012). On the other hand, companies that meet the conditions for bank lending will use the supplier credit to a lesser extent. Bank financing is considered to be cheaper than supplier credit (Huyghebaert et al. 2007).

Empirical research based on these theories has analysed separately or correlated the impact of trade receivables and payables on financial performance. As long as receivables generate temporary cash deficits, it is accepted that there is a negative relationship between the volume of receivables and financial performance. In other words, shortening cash conversion cycles generates higher profitability (Knauer and Wohrmann, 2013; Muscettola, 2015; Öner, 2016; Otuya and Eginiwin, 2017). Without denying these results, Batrancea et al. (2018) also argued that an increase in receivables positively influences financial performance only in conditions of accelerated sales, in which the growth rate of turnover is higher, shortening the cash conversion cycle.

Admitting that a company manages both assets (trade receivables) and liabilities (trade payables) simultaneously, other authors have shown that shorter business cycles are associated with higher profitability and vice versa (Muscettola, 2015). In other words, there is a negative relationship between the net business cycle and profitability (Soenen, 1993; Öner, 2016; Hill, Kelly and Highfield, 2010; Afrifa

and Gyapong, 2017), which requires a reduction in the number of days for trade receivables and an increase in the number of days for trade payables.

Research methodology

In order to ensure the representativeness of the data, we selected only companies producing spare parts for vehicles. The construction of the sample was based on three criteria: sales volume (turnover), size of profits and number of employees. After collecting the data (accessing secondary sources), we eliminated companies that were established after 2009, that recorded losses for more than three consecutive years (in the period 2009-2018) or did not submit financial statements for all 10 years of the period analysed. The final sample consist of 44 companies (of which 3% large companies, organized as joint stock companies, and 97% small and medium enterprises, organized as limited liability companies). The selected companies represent 14.6% of the total companies in the stated fields and generate 60% of the turnover of these fields.

Since most of the companies in the sample are medium-sized companies (unlisted), we turned to ROA (return on assets) and ROE (return on equity) accounting measures. Regarding the independent variables, we included in the analysis *trade receivables*, *trade payables*, and *net trade credit*. Due to the differences in the size of the companies in the sample, we used two control variables: *firm size* and *growth rate*. The variables and the methodology for determining them are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Variables defining

Variables	Cod	Measuring
Return on assets	ROA	Gross profit / Total assets
Return on equity	ROE	Net profit / Shareholder's Equity
Share of receivables in turnover	SR	Trade receivables / Turnover = TR / T
Share of payables in turnover	SP	Trade payables / Turnover = TP / T
Net trade credit	NTC	(TR/Total assets) – (TP/Total assets)
Growth rate	G	Turnover _n / Turnover ₂₀₀₉ (2009 is the base year)
Firm size	S	The natural logarithm of assets

Empirical research is based on the following hypotheses:

H 1. Trade receivables and payables have a negative impact on the financial performance assessed by the ROA and respectively ROE.

H 2. There exists a negative association between net trade credit and financial performance assessed by ROA and respectively ROE.

Results

The analysis at the level of descriptive statistics indicated that ROA and ROE for the sampled companies vary between a negative minimum and a maximum with very high values (73.2% for ROA and 361.7% for ROE). The average level of profitability indicators indicates a very important aspect. The ROE (20.6%) is higher than the ROA (12.0%), which means that the companies in the sample use borrowed funds whose cost is lower than the internal rate of return. The average share of receivables in turnover (SR = 29.6) is lower than the average share of trade payables in turnover (SP = 47.4). Analysis from the perspective of net assets held indicated a negative average NTC, which confirms that, at the sample level, the volume of trade payables is higher than the volume of trade receivables (see Table 2).

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of the independent and dependent variables

	Mean	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.	Observations
ROA	12.083	73.200	-27.900	13.494	440
ROE	20.665	361.400	-100.100	27.729	440
SR	29.602	691.700	1.600	44.951	440
SP	47.403	1321.600	3.000	83.472	440
NTC	-16.147	63.694	-93.533	23.932	440
G	742.982	25058.00	0.100	2724.298	440
First difference of growth rate	157.413	8688.100	-3061.900	783.675	396
Firm size = S	2.94E+08	3.06E+09	716559.0	4.97E+08	440
Logarithm of firm size	17.591	21.841	13.482	2.321	440

Source: processed by the author

In terms of growth rates, the standard deviation indicates a large variation in values, which means that, at the sample level, companies have experienced (over the 10 years) very different growth rates. Regarding the size of the companies in the sample (estimated by logarithmic average annual number of employees), the value spread rate is relatively low which means that they are comparable in size. First difference of growth rate was determined to solve the stationarity problem.

Eviews 9 software was used to perform statistical analyses for econometric models that estimate the impact on ROA and ROE. The analyses are based on the panel data method (OLS adapted to panel data), which is a specific method of generating equations for data containing both time series and cross sections. By determining the correlation matrix of the variables (table 3) we showed that there are no significant correlations (greater than 0.7) between the independent and control variables, which strengthens the fact that they can be used together in the same econometric model.

Table 3. Correlation matrix of the variables considered in the analysis

Variables	ROA	ROE	SR	SP	NTC	G	S
ROA	1.000						
ROE	0.625 (0.000)	1.000					
SR	-0.201 (0.000)	-0.042 (0.376)	1.000				
SP	-0.294 (0.000)	-0.106 (0.025)	0.615 (0.000)	1.000			
NTC	0.374 (0.000)	0.041 (0.379)	0.180 (0.000)	-0.322 (0.000)	1.000		
G	0.091 (0.055)	0.109 (0.021)	-0.058 (0.221)	-0.030 (0.517)	-0.053 (0.260)	1.000	
S	-0.036 (0.450)	-0.024 (0.601)	-0.147 (0.002)	-0.055 (0.247)	-0.125 (0.008)	0.246 (0.000)	1.000

Note: probability in parenthesis
Source: processed by the author

The regression results are summarized in Table 4. The two multiple regression models are statistically significant (R-squared for ROA and ROE is 0.713, respectively, 0.431), and F-statistic probability higher than 0.01 (meaning that the predictors are related significant with the dependent variable). R-square adjusted indicates that 66.6% of the ROA variation is explained by the variation of the independent variables. The second regression model explains the ROE variation only in proportion of 33.7%.

Table 4. Regression analysis

Indicators	Model 1 - ROA	Model 2 -ROE
	Coefficient (Std. error)	Coefficient (Std. error)
Share of receivables in turnover	-0.127*** (0.024)	-0.062 (0.068)
Share of payables in turnover	-0.091*** (0.029)	-0.187** (0.081)
Net trade credit	0.048 (0.041)	-0.386*** (0.116)
First difference of growth rate	0.001* (0.001)	0.005** (0.001)
Logarithm of firm size	0.961 (1.507)	1.147 (4.193)
R-squared	0.713	0.431
Adjusted R-squared	0.666	0.337
F-statistic	15.071***	4.596***

Note: Standard error in parenthesis;

Note: *, ** and *** represents significant values at 1%, 5% respectively 10%

Source: processed by the author

The regression estimate reveals that (in the case of the first model) there is a significant negative relationship between SR, SP and ROA. The second model indicates that there is a significant negative relationship between SP, NTC and ROE. For both models, the turnover growth rate is positively and significantly correlated with the financial performance appreciated by ROA and ROE.

Discussion and conclusions

In the context of intensifying globalization, performance management has taken on the task of ensuring business flexibility and increasing/maintaining competitive advantage. Therefore, trade policy is gaining importance in the context of value creation for both the company and the interested parties. However, a commercial policy focused on attracting/retaining customers (by postponing the payment of invoices) generates an imbalance in the company's cash flow. To the extent that managers effectively manage the receivables and liabilities generated by sales and supply operations (aiming to maintain a short-term financial balance), they can minimize the negative impact on financial performance.

The study aimed to determine the impact of trade receivables and payables on the financial performance assessed by ROA and ROE. Different from previous research (Padachi, 2006; Batrancea et al., 2018), which separately assesses the impact of trade receivables and payables on financial performance, in this study we included a third variable (net trade credit - according to Afrifa and Gyapong, 2017), which indicates the net financial statement resulting from the purchasing and sales operations. Then, in order to ensure the representativeness of the results, we performed an analysis on a relatively homogeneous sample (both in terms of field of activity and in terms of business size).

The results of the statistical analysis partially confirmed two hypotheses: trade receivables and payables have a negative impact on the financial performance assessed by ROA; net trade credit has a significant and negative impact only on ROE. Our results confirm the results of previous research (Hill, Kelly and Highfield, 2010; Muscettola, 2014; Afrifa and Gyapong, 2017), including those conducted on the example of Romanian companies (Batrancea et al, 2018). To increase the efficiency of asset use, managers need to reduce trade receivables and payables. To increase the efficiency of using equity, managers must reduce net trade credit.

Research is useful from at least two points of view: theoretically, because it performs an evaluation of the literature both from the perspective of performance management and from the perspective of theories on company financing; practical, as it provides empirical evidence on the impact of trade

receivables and payables on performance; managers can capitalize the research results to achieve a sound rationale for funding and performance strategies.

References

Afrifa, G., and E. Gyapong

2017

"Net trade credit: what are the determinants?" *International Journal of Managerial Finance*, 13(3): 246-266.

Afrifa, G.A. and K. Padachi

2016

"Working capital level influence on SME profitability." *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 23(1):44-63.

Al-Sa'eed M. A.

2018

"The impact of ownership structure and dividends on firm's performance: evidence from manufacturing companies listed on the Amman Stock Exchange." *Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal*, 12(3):87-106.

Atanasova, C.

2007

"Access to Institutional Finance and the Use of Trade Credit." *Financial Management*, 36(1): 49-67.

Baker H. K., E. T. Veit and G. E. Powell

2001

"Factors influencing dividend policy decisions of NASDAQ firms." *The Financial Review* 36(3):19-37.

Banos-Caballero, S., P. J. Garcia-Teruel and P. Martínez-Solano

2010

"Working capital management in SMEs." *Accounting & Finance*, 50(3):511-527.

Batrancea, I., I. D. Morar, E. Masca, C., Sabau and L. Bechis, 2018, *Econometric Modeling of SME Performance. Case of Romania, Sustainability* 2018, 10, 192:1-15.

Garcia-Teruel, P. J. and P. Martínez-Solano

2010

"A dynamic perspective on the determinants of accounts payable." *Review of Quantitative Finance and Accounting* 34(4): 439-457.

Goddard, J., M. Tavakoli and J.O.S. Wilson

2005

"Determinants of Profitability in European Manufacturing and Services: Evidence from a Dynamic Panel Model." *Applied Financial Economics*, 15:1269-1282.

Hill, M. D., G. W. Kelly and M. J. Highfield

2010

"Net Operating Working Capital Behavior: A First Look." *Financial Management*, 39(2):783-805.

Huyghebaert, N., L. Van de Gucht and C. Van Hulle

2007

"The Choice between Bank Debt and Trade Credit in Business Start-ups." *Small Business Economics*, 29(4): 435-452.

Knauer, T. and A. Wöhrmann

2013

"Working Capital Management and Firm Profitability." *Journal of Management Control*, 24:77-87.

Molina, C.A. and L.A. Preve

2012

"An Empirical Analysis of the Effect of Financial Distress on Trade Credit." *Financial Management*, 41(1):187-205.

Muscettola, M.

2014

"Cash Conversion Cycle and Firm's Profitability: An Empirical Analysis on a Sample of Manufacturing SMEs of Italy." *International Journal of Business and Management*, 9:25-35.

Oner, M.

2016

"The Impact of Working Capital Management on Firm Profitability: Empirical Evidence from Borsa Istanbul." *Journal of Politics, Economics and Management Studies*, 4(3):63-79.

Orozco, L.A., J. Vargas, R. Galindo-Dorado

2018

"Trends on the relationship between board size and financial and reputational corporate performance: The Colombian case." *European Journal of Management and Business Economics*, 27(2):183-197.

Otuya, S. and E.J. Eginwin

2017

Otuya, S. and J. Eginwin. Inventory Management and SMEs Profitability. A Study of Furniture Manufacturing, Wholesale and Eatery Industry in Delta State, Nigeria." *Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 5(3):75-79.

Padachi, K.

2006

Trends in working capital management and its impact on firms' performance: an analysis of Mauritian small manufacturing firms." *International Review of Business Research Papers*, 2(2):45–58.

Peleckis K., M. Krutinis and N. Slavinskaitė

2013

Daugiakriterinis alkoholio pramonės įmonių pagrindinės veiklos efektyvumo vertinimas. Verslo ir teisės aktualijos 1(8):1-16.

Petersen, M. A. and R. G. Rajan

1997

"Trade credit: theories and evidence." *Review of Financial Studies* 10(3): 661-691.

Rajnoha, R., P. Lesníková and A. Korauš

2016

"From Financial Measures to Strategic Performance Measurement System and Corporate Sustainability: Empirical Evidence from Slovakia." *Economics and Sociology* 9(4):134-152.

Soenen, L.

1993

Cash Conversion Cycle and Corporate Profitability. *Journal of Cash Management*, 13: 34-53.

Suhadak, S., K. Kurniaty, S. R. Handayani, S. M. Rahayu

2019

"Stock return and financial performance as moderation variable in influence of good corporate governance towards corporate value." *Asian Journal of Accounting Research*, 4(1):18-34.